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WARUNKI ZAPOBIEGANIA KONFLIKTOM INTERPERSONALNYM STUDENTOM INSTYTUCJI SZKOLNICTWA WYŻSZEGO

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Streszczenie. Autor analizuje podejścia do rozumienia zapobiegania konfliktom interpersonalnym w środowisku studenckim. Wyjaśnia pojęcie „zapobiegania konfliktom”. Określa przyczyny, etapy konfliktów w studentów instytucji szkolnictwa wyższego. Artykuł podkreśla rodzaje, etapy zapobiegania konfliktom interpersonalnym w środowisku studenckim. Autor przeprowadził badanie wśród studentów specjalności „Praca socjalna”, które obejmuje analizę treści programu edukacyjno-zawodowego, planu pracy naukowej, podane wyniki badań eksperymentalnych, przedstawionych w celu określenia zachowania studentów w sytuacjach konfliktowych. Autor podsumowuje potrzebę systematycznego i ukierunkowanego zapobiegania konfliktom interpersonalnym w środowisku studenckim.

Słowa kluczowe: student, konflikt, uniwersytet, przyczyny, zapobieranie, środowisko, praca socjalna.

CONDITIONS OF PREVENTION OF INTERPERSONAL CONFLICT OF STUDENTS OF HIGHER EDUCATION

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Anotation. The author analyzes the approaches to understanding the prevention of interpersonal conflicts in the student environment. Clarifies the concept of "prevention of conflicts". Determines the causes, stages of conflicts in students of institutions of higher education.

The article highlights the stages, stages of prevention of interpersonal conflicts in the student environment. The author conducted a study among the students of the specialty "Social Work", which includes an analysis of the contents of the educational-professional program, the plan of academic work, the results of experimental studies presented to determine the behavior of students in conflict situations. The author concludes the need for systematic and targeted prevention of interpersonal conflicts in the student environment.

Key words: Conflict, pedagogical conflict, prophylaxis, interpersonal interaction, compromise, cooperation, competition, avoidance, resist.

УМОВИ ПРОФІЛАКТИКИ МІЖСОБИСТІСНИХ КОНФЛІКТІВ СТУДЕНТІВ ЗАКЛАДІВ ВИЩОЇ ОСВІТИ

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Анотація. Автор аналізує підходи до розуміння профілактик міжособистісних конфліктів у студентському середовищі. Уточнює поняття «профілактика конфліктів». Визначає причини, етапи виникнення конфліктів у студентів закладів вищої освіти.

В статті виділені види, етапи профілактики міжособистісних конфліктів у студентському середовищі. Автором проведене дослідження серед студентів спеціальності «Соціальна робота», яке включає аналіз змісту освітньо-професійної програми, план навчальної роботи, подані результати експериментальних досліджень для визначення поведінки учнів у конфліктних ситуаціях. Автор робить висновок про необхідність проведення систематичної та цілеспрямованої профілактики міжособистісних конфліктів у студентському середовищі.

Introduction. The success of students in the educational process depends on many factors, including the their character of interpersonal relations in the academic group. Formation and operation of academic groups, as well as any group is not possible without such phenomena as the origin, prevention and conflict resolution

Entering to the university, young people begin a new life, where trained to express themselves, form new goals, objectives and values during functioning of the academic group.

The structure of personal relationships and team structure constantly interact, influence each other and converge more stronger, if better organized joint activities of people. It is known that in the development of any team is its infancy, the conflict period, rule-making, business activity and decay. Especially important in periods of becoming and rule-making groups and provide necessary assistance to first-year students, explain the law and to teach ways to overcome conflict.

Features of conflict prevention in the student team depends on understanding the reasons, procedural aspects of the conflict, its types and functions. Realizing that the conflicts inherent in interpersonal interactions people believe that prevention work on conflicts in interpersonal interactions, students must be made consistently and is aimed to improve communication, optimizing the educational process of identity formation and professionally competent professional using with rational methods of conflict resolution (Grybok, 2014).

The most common type of conflicts among students is the conflict between personality and group. The emergence of it is associated with a situation where one of the groupmates does not want to adhere to established norms of behavior or communication. For example, students are accustomed to always prepare all the questions of a seminar for a couple, but one of their groupmates refuses to do this and inclines others to divide the question. This causes dissatisfaction with most of the group, because if you work in this mode, the level of knowledge will be low. Thus, there is a conflict situation between a group and a person (individual student).

The same kind of conflict is between the group and the old man, when the latter tries to subjugate other students, not taking into account their thoughts and positions.

Such behavior from the side of the old age prevents others from showing themselves, defending their own point of view and taking a decent place in the team. It is known that today our society needs creative, creative people with a non-standard position and vision on the world. Therefore, the emergence of such situations is unacceptable: if they appear, then they need an immediate solution.

At the same time, besides the personal-group conflict in higher education institutions, there is also an intergroup conflict - conflict situations of a student group with representatives of the administration, the dean's office, the trade union committee or with other groups (*Nazarenko, 2009, p.496*).

The problem of conflicts in peer groups, including student groups were engaged in such domestic scientists as E. Durmanenko, I. Zaitsev, Leonid Losev, AP Luzan, and others. The problem also was investigated by foreign scientists, including James. Kaprara, J. Servon, L. Steinberg and others.

Main part. In modern literature, the definition of "conflict prevention" and "prevention of conflicts" are often used as synonyms. We consider it appropriate to distinguish these allegations. Conflict prevention is a broader concept, and preventing conflicts is a form of prevention.

Conflict prevention is a system of managed activities that provides scientific, theoretical and practical implementation of measures aimed at preventing conflicting behavior (*Khersonskii, Dvoryak, 2010, p.199*).

O.Y. Antsupov and O.I. Shipilov, taking into account the negative effects of conflict interaction, noted that conflict prevention is an even more important component than a constructive solution to them. It is possible to avoid negative consequences if timely responding and prevention of conflict situations covering four areas: 1) creating objective conditions that prevent the emergence and destructive development of pre-conflict situations; 2) optimization of organizational and managerial conditions for the creation and operation of organizations; 3) eliminating socio-psychological factors of conflict, 4) blocking personal factors of conflict. As scientists point out, in order for prevention to be successful, all points should be used in direct interaction and simultaneously in all directions (*Antsupov, Shipilov, 1999, p. 241*).

A. Antsupov and A. Shipilov note that social interaction is consistent in the case when it is balanced. They identified five balances, which may cause a conflict to violate.

1. Balance roles. In social interaction, its participants can play each other in the role of senior, equal or younger in their social status. If the communication partners take their roles, there is no role conflict. The highest conflict potential has the role of senior, although it is often psychologically most comfortable for a person. The most favorable in terms of preventing conflicts is the interaction with the environment on equal terms.

2. Balance of interdependence in decisions and actions. All people seek freedom and independence. However, our freedom must not restrict the freedom of those who are near. If one person feels excessive dependence on the other, it can cause discomfort, provoke conflicting behavior.

3. Balance of mutual services. Throughout the life of each person, they help other people and receive help from other people. However, no matter how altruistic feelings a person would be guided by, he deliberately or unknowingly fixed the services that he provided himself or received from others.

4. Balance of losses. People have a sense of revenge: if we suffer damage as a result of other people's actions, we also want to cause some kind of damage to the guilty

person. The task of damage can break the relationship and become the basis for the emergence of conflict.

5. Balance of self-assessment and external evaluation. In the process of social interaction, people are constantly evaluated by each other. The most intensive process of mutual evaluation takes place in the dyad "subordinate leader", "teacher-student".

6. D.G. Scott allocates a balance of responsibility. In her opinion, a situation in which one of the parties assumes too much or too little responsibility is potentially a conflict. In the first case, an individual who has taken too much responsibility may experience overload, fatigue due to the need to perform extra work and lack of support. If liability is too small, one may feel reduced its significance, dependence on others and loss of individuality. In both cases, there may be feelings of insult and annoyance that underlie the conflict. Consequently, one of the conditions for the prevention of conflicts is the fair distribution of responsibility (*Antsupov, Shipilov, 1999, p. 241*).

Most scientists allocate primary and secondary prevention of conflicts among students. These types of conflict preventionscientists believe, the need to provide as external (primarily organizational and administrative measures), as internal or proper warning of the psychosocial measures.

Primary prevention of conflicts in interpersonal interactions provides students the conflictological education and development of the conflict potential or actual participants. Repeated (secondary) prevention of conflict include direct work in risk groups, relieve tension, confrontation, in groups with high potential for conflict and escalation of conflicts.

Analysis of the above, allows us to conclude that the most effective is approach by E. Durmanenko, that along with prevention activities to update the constructive conflict resolution, which are difficult to understand conscious purposeful influence on the clash of parties in conflict at all stages of its origin , development and completion to prevent destructive conflicts and resolve them constructively (*Durmanenko, 2004, p. 23*).

In prevention work to prevent conflicts among students used different methods.

The methods of preventing interpersonal conflicts, E. Durmanenko defines the following:

- cognitive - clear and specific clarification of positions, relationships, concepts; provide feedback; collect additional information

- motivational - forecasting perspective; common constructive solution to the problem of competition or cooperation

- Active - increase of efficiency of joint activity

- organizational - increasing flexibility and roles dynamic (*Durmanenko, 2004, p. 25*).

An effective method of prophylaxis and conflict prevention, according to V. Andreyev, avoiding the typical conflicts. In particular, he recommended to observe the following behavior: do not seek to dominate anything; be a principal, but not only fight for principles; remember that straightforwardness - is good, but not always; often smile (smile was worth valued but expensive); remember that tradition - it is good to a certain extent; you need to tell the truth, but this must be done skillfully; strive to be independent, but not arrogant; not to turn to pragmatism pragmatism; do not expect justice for yourself if thou wicked; do not overestimate their abilities and capabilities; do not take the initiative where it does not need; to show goodwill; to exercise restraint and calm in any situation; realize itself in the work and not in conflict. Please also note that the most positive feature of the conflict is that it is a source of development and gives an opportunity improve the situation (*Anczupov, 2007, p. 19*).

Analyses of plans of educational and educational work of students of Lesya Ukrainka Eastern European National University demonstrates that prophylaxis of conflicts in interpersonal interactions of students is carried systematically and comprehensively.

Formation of the conflictological culture of students, which includes a system of knowledge, a system of educational work (learning disciplines educational degree "bachelor" specialty "Social pedagogy" - "Fundamentals of educational Conflict" (course) "Psycho-pedagogical foundations of interpersonal communication" (year), "Self-education and self-regulation of the individual" (course), educational degree "Master" specialty "social work" - "conflict management in socio-pedagogical process" (120 hour, classroom - 42 hrs.), educational degree "Master" specialty "Pedagogy of higher school" (90 hrs., classroom - 36 h.)

The purpose of these educational courses is to develop knowledge on the causes, mechanisms of pedagogical conflicts and ways of their prevention and constructive solution, specific conflict management in socio-pedagogical process and of their acquisition of skills to control the conflict situation, diagnose conflict constructively to solve it; positively perceive the conflict and its pragmatic use it in educational activities.

In the process of study mentioned above disciplines students form the knowledge about the nature of conflict as phenomenal phenomenon of social development, its structure, functions and types; acquainted with the specific features of teaching conflict and the mechanism of a social and educational environment, including high school; analyze the main konfliktogeny in the pedagogical process of high school; analyze different ways of solving pedagogical conflicts; learn to predict the occurrence of teaching conflict constructively to solve it, and effectively manage the conflict in the pedagogical process

Accordingly, the goal is only possible on the mastering of knowledge, patterns and characteristics of education; principles of education and ways of their realization in the educational process; organizational forms and methods of education; method of forming a student group; the nature, role and importance of student government in high school; basic historical stages of the conflict theory; current concepts and research areas in Conflict as a whole and particularly in educational Conflict; Specific features of the conflicts in the socio-pedagogical process; the nature and structure of teaching conflict, its features and characteristics, diagnosis; typology of pedagogical conflicts and their dynamics; basic styles of behavior in conflict situations and how to address the structural social and educational conflict; and skills, trained to plan process in higher education; apply optimal organizational forms and methods of education for its main areas; Students rally kolektyvanalizuvaty conflicts, identify the conflict issue, the conflict, overt and hidden interests and concerns; analyze conflictogen (communication, trust, content, technology, etc.) educational system; predict conflict in the pedagogical environment; determine the phase of the conflict; plat teaching conflict; resolve conflicts constructively teaching in different ways; choose the best style of behavior in conflict situations; effectively manage teaching conflict.

This knowledge students embody and improve the process of course, diploma and master's studies, the result of writing which is to develop training programs, interactive methods of prevention of various conflicts that are used in educational work with students to practice in educational institutions and social services.

Participation in the organization of educational activities:

- in academic groups, according to the work plan curator;

- at the Faculty of Education, according to the plan of educational work of the Faculty;

- General university, according to the plan of educational work Lesya Ukrainka Eastern European National University

Attracting students to the activities of structural subdivisions of the student government, cooperation with civil society organizations, which is coordinated by the Department of Youth Policy and Social Work Lesya Ukrainka Eastern European National University. The aim of this partnership are:

- comprehensive support spiritual and physical development of students, instilling in them a sense of civic consciousness and patriotism

- enforcement of orders and instructions, guidance letters on the problems of youth policy and educational work.

- development of proposals to improve organizational and functional structure of management of educational process at the University and the definition of the functional responsibilities of management

- coordination of structural subdivisions, student government and cooperation with civil society organizations in matters of youth and educational work.

- promoting broad involvement of students in the activities of the student government, the development of progressive forms of government

- study of the problems of students and the creation of necessary conditions for full youth organizations and social formation of youth

Social activities implemented by students during their activities in different associations in terms Lesya Ukrainka Eastern European National University, Student Council, Volunteer Center "Dovira" Youth Policy Council, the Council of young scientists, sports clubs, art groups and others. Participation in these associations on the one hand generates socially active students on the other side - in the absence of conflictological culture creates the conditions for confrontation, unhealthy competition and conflicts of interest of students.

To identify the effectiveness of the prevention of conflicts in interpersonal interactions students of specialty "Social work" and "Pedagogy of high school" we have the study of conflict detection level students. The study involved 42 students, including 22 students of 1 year and 10 students of the 5th year full-time specialty "Social work", 10 students of 6 courses of specialty "Pedagogy of high school."

We conducted research offered students "Research Methodology response characteristics in a conflict situation" K.Tomasa (adaptation N.V.Hryshynoyi) (*Lozhkin, 2002, p. 105*). Method to determine the typical ways of responding to conflict situations and contains 5 scales, describing ways to respond to conflict situations (Table 1.):

Table 1.

Characteristics of ways of behavior in conflict situations

Ways of behavior	Characteristics
Rivalry	characterized by the desire to achieve satisfaction of their interests at the expense of the other
Cooperation	occurs when participants come to the alternative situation that fully meets the interests of both parties
Compromis	characterized by reaching an agreement, in which both sides are certain damages
Avoidance	characterized by a lack of desire of cooperation and lack trend own goals
Adaptation	Characterized by disregard for their own interests of another

Each of these five ways of behavior described by 12 th judgments about individual behavior in conflict situations. In various combinations, they are grouped into 30 pairs, each of which examined choose that judgment, which is a typical characteristic of his behavior. Results of research at picture 1.

Picture 1. The ways of behavior in conflict situations

As we can see on table 1 the way of behavior in a conflict situation with "cooperation" is inherent in the fifth and sixth students rate (40%), "compromise" is used 30% of students and 20% respectively. First-year students at conflict resolution using the "adaptation" (27.3%). Thus, the first-year students tend to devices, avoidance, compromise and competition in a conflict situation, the least they share cooperation. Students in the fifth and sixth course most peculiar behavior as a way to cooperation and compromise.

Conclusions. An analysis of the prevention of conflicts in interpersonal interactions students Lesya Ukrainka Eastern European National University and the Department of Social Education and Pedagogy of high school presents us with a system of lines of prevention in the context of improving the conflict of culture and humanization of relations partners of which affects the quality of teaching and educational work, prevention of destructive forms of social behavior in the conflict, which is essential for optimizing social and educational factors, educational interaction among students.

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